

Your Open Science Journey

You, the researcher:

how you and your work are discovered, made visible and gets recognition

Your Research Team/Lab:

how you can work openly

Your Community:

improve interoperability, sharing, and reuse beyond your team

Beyond Your Community:

preparing for cross-domain challenges

Take the first steps on your journey to Open Science

Useful checklists for you, the researcher

Your Digital Presence

Data Documentation and Citation Checklist

Software Documentation and Citation Checklist

Useful checklists for your research team

Open Science Practices for Teams

Resources and Guides for Teams

Digital Objects Preservation Checklist for Teams